

Measurements of Turbulence in Katabatic Winds over a Steep Slope

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Research Project

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What are the Katabatic Winds?

- Downslope winds or gravity currents.
- Found in mountainous regions and in presence of a slope.
- Cooled by radiative processes near the ground.
- Calm clear nights -> Anticyclonic conditions.

Why are they relevant?

- Fill the bottom of valleys with cold air.
- Influence the local weather and the dispersion of pollutants in the valleys.
- Are not well represented in weather forecasting and climate models.

Objective

Characterize episodes of Katabatic Wind on a steep slope, with better spacial resolution (more instruments).

Observational Site & Field Campaign

- Grand Colon, Belledone Massif.
- At 1770 m.
- Relatively homogeneous slope of 30° .
- Alpine pasture area: low vegetation and sparse rocks and pebbles.
- Campaign from 12-28 Feb.
- Anticyclonic episode

Instrumentation

Theory

Reynolds decomposition:

Covariance: Common relationship between two variables

$$\begin{aligned}\text{covar}(A, B) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} a'_i b'_i, \\ &= \overline{a' b'}.\end{aligned}$$

Momentum and Heat Fluxes

Sensible heat flux

$$H = \rho C_p \overline{w'\theta'},$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{U}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{U}_j \frac{\partial \bar{U}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\delta_{i3}g + f_c \epsilon_{ij3} \bar{U}_j - \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\nu \partial^2 \bar{U}_i}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{\partial(\bar{u}_i' \bar{u}_j')}{\partial x_j}$$

How heat is being transported in the vertical

Momentum flux

$$F = \rho \overline{u'w'}$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial t} + \bar{U}_j \frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\nu_\theta \partial^2 \bar{\theta}}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{1}{\bar{\rho} C_p} \frac{\partial \bar{Q}_j^*}{\partial x_j} - \frac{L_v E}{\bar{\rho} C_p} - \frac{\partial(\bar{u}_j' \bar{\theta}')}{\partial x_j}$$

How momentum is being transported in the vertical

Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE)

Definition

$$e = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2} + \overline{w'^2}).$$

- Summed velocity variances divided by two
- Kinetic energy of the flow into a portion associated with the mean wind (MKE), and a portion associated with the turbulence (TKE).
- Measurement of intensity of turbulence.

Methodology

30 min. averages

Temperature,
wind speed
and wind direction

**Detecting katabatic
wind episodes**

Calibration

Comparison between:

CSAT3 & *Thermocouple*
temperature

CSAT3 & *Windsonic*
wind speed.

5 min. averages

Compute TKE and
Turbulent Fluxes

Software used: EddyPro and Python.

Temperature time series

Green shadows are the suggested periods

Wind speed time series

Thermocouple vs. CSAT3

Wind speed

Vertical profiles Temperature and Wind Speed

Night of 23-24 Feb.

30 min. average

Vertical profiles Temperature and Wind Speed

Night of 23-24 Feb.

30 min. average

Vertical profiles TKE and Fluxes

Night of 23-24 Feb.

5 min. average

Vertical profiles Temperature and Wind Speed

Night of 16-17 Feb.

30 min. average

Vertical profiles TKE and Fluxes

Night of 16-17 Feb.

5 min. average

Conclusions

- The calibration done between the different type instruments showed that there was consistency between the temperature of the Thermocouples and the CSAT3 and wind speed between Windsonic and CSAT3.
- Maximum wind speed was located below 1m of height. In [0.5m, 0.75m].
- The momentum flux profiles showed a negative flux for the levels below the wind maximum and a positive flux above the maximum.
- Sensible heat flux, all the profiles were negative because of the stable environment, but there were some variations when the profiles should remain constant that are difficult to explain.

Thank you

Extra slides

Data source	H (m)	\bar{U} (m s ⁻¹)	$\overline{\Delta\theta}$ (K)	\dot{L} (m)	Slope sin α (%)
Martin (1975, Fig. 3) 20 September 1970	2	2.4	2.5	1100	12
6 September 1970 (Figs. 6, 8)	2	2.8	3.5	1100	12
Ohata and Higuchi (1979) 5 September 1975	3	1.6	3.25	200	15
3 July 1975	3	2.9	2	700	17
Manins and Sawford (1979b, Fig. 6)	45	2.7	4	4000	6.1
Mahrt and Larsen (1982 Fig. 3)	10	1.0	2.2	400	3.5
Munro and Davies (1977, Fig. 3)	6	4.4	3.2	5000	5
Lettau (1966)	8	2.7	4.5	2×10^5	0.17

Vertical profiles

Night of 16 Feb.

